

Development of a simplified comfort evaluation tool for multi-objective evaluation analysis of building energy retrofit strategies

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Energy renovation in buildings is a multi-objective project that targets low energy demand and high indoor thermal comfort. This study aims to investigate multiple energy retrofit interventions, including thermal insulation, highly insulative window systems, mechanical ventilation for cooling, and shading, and to define the optimum retrofit strategy for various building topologies. For this purpose, a simplified decision tool, THESEAS (Thermal comfort and Energy analysis for Sustainable and Efficient renovAtion Solutions) is developed, requesting basic input regarding a building's geometry, boundary conditions, and materials, to calculate the yearly energy savings for heating and cooling and enhance indoor thermal comfort conditions achieved by a retrofit strategy. Indoor thermal comfort is defined by calculating suitable thermal comfort indexes that refer to the Predicted Mean Vote (PMV) and the Predicted Percentage of Dissatisfied (PPD). THESEAS tool compares and defines the optimum retrofit scenario that simultaneously results in the maximum decrease in the yearly energy demand and the greatest enhancement of the building's indoor thermal environment. The multi-objective analysis of the developed tool is based on the simulation engine of EnergyPlus, which is used to perform yearly dynamic simulations and provide accurate results. This study considers a one-story residential building located in the city of Athens, Greece. According to the calculations, the four-intervention retrofit strategy results in an 11.8% and 56.1% decrease in the building's heating and cooling energy demand, respectively, while an annual enhancement of 16.6% in the building's thermal comfort PPD index is calculated.

Keywords: Building energy retrofit, energy savings, thermal comfort, multi-objective evaluation

INTRODUCTION

The combined examination of a building's energy performance and indoor thermal comfort conditions is essential for the achievement of low energy consumption and the occupant's well-being. Thermal comfort is the state of being satisfied with a building's thermal environment, allowing occupants to remain comfortable without adjusting conditions [1]. Unfortunately, the continuous rise in energy prices, coupled with inflationary pressures in the consumer goods and services market, persistently erodes household financial stability, putting them at risk of energy poverty [2]. Combined with the increasing phenomena of cold and, especially, hot extremes, a severe threat to human health has arisen.

Maintaining healthy and comfortable living conditions should not come at the expense of reducing energy consumption in buildings. Implementing passive building envelope retrofit technologies results in the mitigation of a building's energy consumption, as well as in the enhancement of its indoor environment [3]. Thermal insulation is a conventional retrofit measure that is reported to mitigate both energy consumption and thermal comfort dissatisfaction

in buildings [4]. Moreover, according to a study by Hu et al. [5], the implementation of passive cooling retrofit techniques that relate to a building's windows systems and the incoming solar irradiation are crucial to a building's indoor air temperature distribution and cooling thermal loads. The installation of fixed, external shading elements on a building's glazing components is currently the predominant solution for mitigating solar heat gains and enhancing visual comfort [6]. Additionally, the installation of a mechanical ventilation system for cooling purposes can effectively decrease a building's cooling energy demand and enhance its indoor thermal comfort conditions [7]. However, the standalone implementation of mechanical ventilation systems cannot sufficiently meet the energy and thermal comfort requirements in the hot Mediterranean climates [8] and therefore should be implemented as part of an expanded building energy renovation strategy.

A thermally neutral indoor environment is a subjective definition, determined by multiple health and physical parameters [9]. Multiple thermal comfort evaluation models are constantly being developed based on different regression models and sampling inspections. Fanger's

thermal comfort model is categorized among the oldest and most widely recognized ones, based on a foundational approach for analysing thermal conditions [10]. This model incorporates the six key factors of air dry-bulb temperature, radiant temperature, air velocity, humidity, metabolic rate, and clothing insulation to compute generalized thermal comfort indices based on the ASHRAE [1] thermal sensation scale.

The objective of this analysis is to simultaneously assess energy efficiency savings and thermal comfort enhancements through various renovation actions, applied individually and in combination, in a typical building. The selected renovation actions to be investigated include thermal insulation, highly insulative windows, mechanical ventilation for cooling and shading. This study aims to identify the most effective renovation strategies from two perspectives, energy efficiency and thermal comfort, and to offer guidelines on the overall benefits of renovation procedures. For this purpose, the developed THESEAS tool, which is an EnergyPlus-based, simplified decision tool is used. The conclusions of this work can be utilized as an asset for future renovation solutions, supporting sustainable urban design, reducing energy consumption, and promoting energy sufficiency in the building sector.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Description of the building

The examined building is a one-story residential building with a floor area of 50 m² and 3 m internal height, which is partially insulated, semi-exposed to ambient air, and located in Athens, Greece. The south and east walls and the building rooftop are adjacent to ambient air, while the rest of the surfaces are in contact with neighboring, thermally treated apartments. Therefore, the boundary condition is considered adiabatic. The window-to-wall ratio equals 25% for the south wall and 15% for the east wall. The absorbance and emittance values of the external surfaces are set to 0.6 and 0.8, respectively [11].

For the baseline scenario, the U-values of the external walls and rooftop are equal to 0.682 W/(m²·K) and 0.629 W/(m²·K), respectively. The windows are double-glazed, with a total U-value of 2.5 W/(m²·K) and a g-value of 0.8. The residence is occupied by two people, with a specific load per occupant equal to 80 W, while the average occupancy factor is 75% [11].

Additionally, the lighting and appliances' specific loads are set to 2 W/m² and 3 W/m², with average operation factors of 39% and 48% [12], respectively. The infiltration rate is considered equal to 0.8 ach [12]. Tab. 1 summarizes the building's geometric and operational data.

Table 1. Geometric and operation data of the examined residence

Parameters	Values
Floor area [m ²]	50
Internal height [m]	3
South wall window-to-wall ratio [%]	25
East wall window-to-wall ratio [%]	15
External wall's U-value [W/m ² ·K]	0.628
Rooftop U-value [W/m ² ·K]	0.629
Windows U-value [W/m ² ·K]	2.5
Windows g-value	0.8
Absorbance of external surfaces	0.6
Emittance of external surfaces	0.8
Infiltration rate [ach]	0.8
Occupants	2
Specific load per occupant [W]	80
Occupancy average factor [%]	75
Specific load for lighting [W/m ²]	2
Mean operation factor for lighting [%]	39
Specific load for appliances [W/m ²]	3
Mean operation factor for appliances [%]	48

Description of examined scenarios

For the formulation of the various renovation scenarios, four different passive envelope retrofit technologies are investigated, either individually or in combination. Specifically, the investigated actions include the installation of:

- i) 6 cm of thermal insulation with thermal conductivity of 0.29 W/(m·K) on the building's envelope external surfaces,
- ii) triple-glazed argon-filled low-e windows with a total U-value of 1.0 W/(m²·K) and a g-value of 0.65,
- iii) mechanical ventilation for cooling with a summer-period operation and an internal minimum air temperature setpoint of 24°C and an external maximum air temperature

setpoint of 26°C, increasing air change rate by up to 1.0 ach,

- iv) external static horizontal shading elements on the building's windows.

All possible combinations among the examined retrofit actions result in 15 separate renovation scenarios, as given in Tab.2. Specifically, four scenarios examine the four renovation actions of thermal insulation (Ins), triple-glazed argon-filled low-e windows (Win), mechanical ventilation system for cooling (Vent) and horizontal external shading element to windows (Shad), as standalone retrofit interventions. Also, six two-intervention renovation scenarios, four three-intervention renovation scenarios, and one four-intervention renovation scenario are investigated. Including the baseline scenario, there are 16 scenarios in total.

Table 2. Description of renovation scenarios

Scenario	Ins	Win	Vent	Shad
#1-1	✓			
#1-2		✓		
#1-3			✓	
#1-4				✓
#2-1	✓	✓		
#2-2	✓		✓	
#2-3	✓			✓
#2-4		✓	✓	
#2-5		✓		✓
#2-6			✓	✓
#3-1	✓	✓	✓	
#3-2	✓	✓		✓
#3-3	✓		✓	✓
#3-4		✓	✓	✓
#4	✓	✓	✓	✓

Simulation strategy

The energy and thermal comfort calculations are performed using the DesignBuilder software [13] and the EnergyPlus simulation program [14]. The timestep is set to 5 minutes according to sensitivity analysis. Additionally, the TARP algorithm is selected for the calculation of the indoor and outdoor

convective heat transfer coefficients. The comparative simulation analysis is performed for the climatic conditions of Athens, Greece [37°58'54"N, 23°43'51"E], retrieved from the DesignBuilder weather library. For Athens, the ambient air temperature varies between 2.0°C and 37.0°C, while the average yearly air temperature is equal to 18.0°C. The heating period lasts from November to the middle of April, while the cooling period is between the last days of May to the middle of September.

Basic equations

The predicted mean vote (PMV) is calculated as a deviation of an occupant's total specific energy loss (L) from its specific rate of metabolism (M), according to the following equation [15]:

$$PMV = (0.303 \cdot E^{-0.036 \cdot M} + 0.028) \cdot (M - L) \quad (1)$$

The thermal comfort equation is based on a regression analysis of steady-state experimental data. Fanger's model quantifies thermal sensation by measuring deviation from optimal comfort conditions. The Predicted Percentage of Dissatisfied (PPD) is calculated as [15]:

$$PPD = 100 - 95 \cdot E^{(-0.03353 \cdot PMV^4 - 0.2179 \cdot PMV^2)} \quad (2)$$

For the calculation of the thermal comfort indexes, the metabolic rate of occupants is considered equal to 58.2 W/m², while the clothing insulation varies between 1.5 clo or 0.2325 (m²·K/W) for the colder winter months and 0.5 clo or 0.0775 (m²·K)/W for summer [3].

RESULTS

Firstly, the baseline scenario is investigated. According to Fig. 1, the yearly heating energy demand is calculated at 2,483 kWh, while the cooling energy demand is at 3,290 kWh. The maximum heating load is found at 2.41 kW on the 27th of December, and the maximum cooling load at 2.99 kW on the 26th of August. The building is described as cooling energy intensive, with is justified by the fact that both its rooftop and south wall as exposed to solar irradiation, and therefore the amount of solar heat gains are an important part of the building energy equilibrium.

Following that, the multi-objective evaluation of the 15 different renovation scenarios is performed. Firstly, the renovation scenarios are compared in terms of heating energy savings and decrease in the PPD index during the heating period, as illustrated in Fig. 2. The renovation scenarios that result in increasing the building's heating energy demand and discomfort during the heating season are scenarios #1-4 (Shad), #2-5 (Win and Shad), #2-6 (Vent and Shad), and #3-4 (Win, Vent and Shad). On the other hand, the most efficient renovation scenarios are calculated to be scenarios #2-1 (Ins and Win) and #3-1 (Ins, Win, and Vent), which are practically identical since the mechanical ventilation system only operates during the cooling season. The addition of thermal insulation and the replacement of windows is the optimum renovation strategy for heating purposes, calculated to result in a 31.1% reduction in the heating energy demand and a 14.4% decrease in the PPD index.

Figure 1. Heating and cooling load and cumulative energy demand for the baseline scenario

Regarding the cooling period, Fig. 3 compares the renovation scenarios in terms of cooling energy savings and the decrease in thermal discomfort. The least effective renovation scenarios are the three one-intervention scenarios, #1-1 (Ins), #1-2 (Win), and #1-3 (Vent). Mechanical ventilation as a standalone retrofit action results in 12.2% cooling energy savings and a 3.5% decrease in the PPD index for the

summer period. If combined with shading (#2-6), cooling energy savings equal 39.9%, and the decrease in PPD is 14.0%. Furthermore, the three-intervention scenario #3-3 (Ins, Vent, and Shad) results in 49.6% reduced energy demand and 22.1% better thermal comfort conditions. The optimum renovation scenario for cooling purposes combines all four retrofit technologies, resulting in 54.1% energy savings and 24.4% enhancement in the summer indoor thermal comfort conditions.

Figure 2. Multi-objective evaluation of the heating energy savings and the decrease in the PPD index for the heating period

Figure 3. Multi-objective evaluation of the cooling energy savings and the decrease in the PPD index for the cooling period

Finally, a multi-objective evaluation is performed comparing the renovation scenarios in terms of annual energy savings and decrease in discomfort. The results are illustrated in Fig.4. The one-intervention scenarios #1-2, #1-3, and #1-4 are found to be the three least effective renovation strategies. The annual optimum renovation scenario involves all four retrofit technologies, resulting in yearly energy savings of 35.9% and a decrease in the PPD index equal to 16.6%. The second-best scenario is #3-2 (Ins, Vent, and Shad), with 31.2% energy savings and 14.9% enhancement in thermal comfort. Based on graphical observation, the renovation scenarios are divided into two subgroups. The first subgroup reaches a maximum, with scenario #1-1, of 16.6% in energy savings and 6.9% in the PPD decrease. The second group outperforms the first one, scoring a minimum decrease of 23.9% in energy demand and 9.9% in the PPD index, which corresponds to scenario #2-2. It is important to notice that every renovation scenario that belongs to the second group involves the retrofit action of thermal insulation. The only exception is the one-intervention scenario #1-1, which belongs to the first group of less effective renovation strategies.

Figure 4. Multi-objective evaluation of the annual energy savings and the decrease in the PPD index

Based on the results of the multi-objective evaluation process, Fig.5 illustrates the annual energy demand and calculated PPD index for the optimum one-intervention (Ins), two-intervention (Ins and Shad), three-intervention (Ins, Win, and Shad), and four-intervention scenarios. This figure

aids in prioritizing the implementation of renovation technologies, identifying thermal insulation as the top priority, followed by shading, windows, and finally, mechanical ventilation systems for cooling. It is useful to state that the incorporation of insulation is vital for reducing the heating loads, while the addition of shading elements is the most important action for mitigating cooling energy loads. However, the application of shading and the restriction of the incoming solar irradiation during the winter period results in significant heating penalties. Therefore, a proper analysis is needed to balance the benefits and drawbacks of shading, a technique that is generally recommended for the climate conditions of Greece. Moreover, the multiple application of renovation actions is calculated to be more effective in improving a building's indoor thermal comfort conditions. Specifically, the PPD index of the baseline scenario is found at 10.97%, while for the four-intervention renovation scenario, it is reduced to 9.15%.

Fig.5. Energy demand and PPD index of the annual optimum, one-, two-, three- and four-intervention retrofit strategies

The energy analysis calculations of the baseline and the optimum renovation scenario are depicted in Fig. 6. Specifically, the hourly heating and cooling loads for the baseline and optimum renovation scenarios are given. According to the calculations, for the optimum renovation scenario, the maximum heating load is equal to 1.66 kW, 22.6% decreased compared to the baseline

scenario, while the maximum cooling load is calculated at 1.96 kW, 34.6% reduced compared to the baseline scenario. The cumulative heating energy demand of the optimum scenario is found at 2,191.1 kWh, 11.8% reduced compared to the baseline scenario. Correspondingly, the cumulative cooling energy demand of the optimum scenario is found at 1,509.5 kWh, 54.1% reduced compared to the baseline scenario. Therefore, it is obvious that all the energy indices are enhanced through the application of all four renovation actions. Despite the application of the cooling techniques, the addition of thermal insulation and high-performance window systems, counterbalance the heating penalty induced by shading and finally result in heating energy savings.

Figure 6. Comparison of heating and cooling loads for baseline and optimum renovation scenario

Finally, the hourly PMV and PPD index calculations for the baseline and four-intervention scenarios are given in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8. The enhancement in the indoor thermal environment is evident throughout the entire year, especially during the summer. During the middle of April and the end of October, the PPD index receives the highest values for both scenarios. These periods are characterized as transitional periods with very low heating or cooling loads, as shown in Fig. 6. The high values of the PPD index can be attributed to the inappropriate selection of light clothing input defined in this analysis. Despite this result, the four-intervention scenario demonstrates better thermal conditions, even during the

transitional periods of the year. Specifically, according to the PMV calculations, the optimum scenario results in warmer indoor conditions (higher values of PMV) during the transitional period of spring, and correspondingly cooler indoor conditions (lower values of PMV) during the transitional period of autumn. Regarding the entire year, the average absolute deviation from the zero value of PMV, which corresponds to a thermally neutral indoor environment, is equal to 0.49 for the baseline, and 0.40 for the optimum renovation scenario, resulting in a difference of 0.09.

Figure 7. Comparison of PMV index for baseline and optimum renovation scenario

Figure 8. Comparison of PPD index for baseline and optimum renovation scenario

CONCLUSIONS

The present work investigates the impact of different renovation actions in a typical building in Athens, Greece. The analysis aims to determine the energy savings in terms of heating and cooling loads, as well as the estimation of the thermal comfort conditions improvement in every case. According to the results, the annually optimum renovation scenario in terms of energy savings and thermal comfort conditions is the scenario that combines all four retrofit technologies. For this scenario, the annual energy savings are calculated at 35.9%, the decrease in the PPD at 16.6%, and the decrease in the average absolute PMV value at 0.09. Additionally, the maximum heating and cooling loads are restricted by 34.6% and 11.8%, respectively.

For the heating period, the two-intervention scenario of thermal insulation and window replacement is found to induce the maximum decrease in heating energy demand, equal to 31.1%, and the maximum decrease in thermal discomfort, equal to 14.4%. On the other hand, for the cooling period, the combination of all four passive building envelope technologies results in a 54.1% reduction in cooling energy demand and a 24.4% enhanced indoor thermal environment.

The addition of thermal insulation is identified as a top-priority renovation action because it is involved in the one-, two-, three- and of course, four-intervention optimum renovation scenarios. Shading ranks as second, window replacement as third, and finally, the mechanical ventilation system as the fourth-priority renovation action. The installation of shading elements and mechanical ventilation systems are characterized as cooling retrofit techniques, between which shading is calculated to be more energy and thermal-comfort-effective. Thermal insulation and highly insulative windows are characterised as heating renovation actions. However, in contrast to shading, thermal insulation and highly-insulative windows do not result in cooling penalties or increase in thermal discomfort.

The conclusions of this analysis can inform future research on selecting renovation actions for different building types, particularly those with seasonal operation, such as hotels, and buildings in various climate zones. In future work, this study will be expanded to include different building typologies and climate conditions.

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NOMENCLATURE

ach – air changes per hour;
L - human-specific thermal losses, W/m²;
M - specific metabolic rate, W/m²;
U-value – Thermal transmittance, W/(m²·K).

Abbreviations

Ins – Thermal insulation renovation action;
PMV - Predicted Mean Vote;
PPD - Predicted Percentage of Dissatisfied;
Shad - Shading renovation action;
Vent - Mechanical ventilation renovation action;
Win - Replacement of windows renovation action.

REFERENCES

- [1] **ASHRAE Handbook-Fundamentals.** Available: <https://www.ashrae.org/technical-resources/ashrae-handbook/description-2021-ashrae-handbook-fundamentals>
- [2] **M. Kola-Bezka**, “One size fits all? Prospects for developing a common strategy supporting European Union households in times of energy crisis,” *Energy Rep.*, vol. 10, pp. 319–332, Nov. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.egyr.2023.06.039.
- [3] **A. Kitsopoulou, D. Pallantzias, C. Sarmoutos, P. Lykas, E. Bellos, M. Gr. Vrachopoulos, C. Tzivanidis**, “A comparative investigation of building rooftop retrofit actions using an energy and computer fluid dynamics approach,” *Energy Build.*, vol. 315, p. 114326, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.enbuild.2024.114326.
- [4] **R.Z. Homod, A. Almusaed, A. Almssad, M.K. Jaafar, M. Goodarzi, and K.S.M. Sahari**, “Effect of different building envelope materials on thermal comfort and air-conditioning energy savings: A case study in Basra city, Iraq,” *J. Energy Storage*, vol. 34, p. 101975, Feb. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.est.2020.101975.
- [5] **M. Hu, K. Zhang, Q. Nguyen, and T. Tasdizen**, “The effects of passive design on indoor thermal comfort and energy savings for residential buildings in hot climates: A systematic

review,” *Urban Clim.*, vol. 49, p. 101466, May 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.uclim.2023.101466.

[6] **A. Alajmi, F. Aba-alkhail, and A. ALAnzi**, “Determining the optimum fixed solar-shading device for minimizing the energy consumption of a side-lit office building in a scorching climate,” *J. Eng. Res.*, vol. 9, no. 2, Art. no. 2, May 2021, doi: 10.36909/jer.v9i2.10773.

[7] **J. Lyu, Y. Yang, D. Lai, L. Lan, Z. Zhao, H. Du, and Z. Lian**, “Analysis of occupant thermal comfort and energy-saving potential based on cooling behaviors in residential buildings: A case study of Shanghai,” *Build. Environ.*, p. 112792, Feb. 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.buildenv.2025.112792.

[8] **M. Maiques, J. Tarragona, M. Gangoells, and M. Casals**, “Energy implications of meeting indoor air quality and thermal comfort standards in Mediterranean schools using natural and mechanical ventilation strategies,” *Energy Build.*, vol. 328, p. 115076, Feb. 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.enbuild.2024.115076.

[9] **Z. Wang, Y. Yang, C. Liu, F. Zhou, and H. Hao**, “Human thermal comfort model and evaluation on building thermal environment,” *Energy Build.*, vol. 323, p. 114796, Nov. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.enbuild.2024.114796.

[10] **Q. Zhao, Z. Lian, and D. Lai**, “Thermal comfort models and their developments: A review,” *Energy Built Environ.*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 21–33, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.enbenv.2020.05.007.

[11] **Technical Guidelines of Technical Chamber of Greece**, TEE. Accessed: Jan. 09, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://web.tee.gr/>

[12] **A. Kitsopoulou, E. Bellos, C. Sammoutos, P. Lykas, M.G. Vrachopoulos, and C. Tzivanidis**, “A detailed investigation of thermochromic dye-based roof coatings for Greek climatic conditions,” *J. Build. Eng.*, vol. 84, p. 108570, May 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.job.2024.108570.

[13] **DesignBuilder Software Ltd.** Accessed: Nov. 28, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://designbuilder.co.uk/>

[14] **EnergyPlus**. Accessed: Oct. 06, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://energyplus.net>

[15] **Engineering Reference - EnergyPlus 22.1**, Available: <https://bigladdersoftware.com/epx/docs/22-1/engineering-reference>